

Supplementary Fig. S3. Effect of small-size tyrosine kinase inhibitors on trastuzumab-sensitive and -resistant cells.

Supplementary Figure S3. Effect of small-size tyrosine kinase inhibitors on trastuzumab-sensitive and -resistant cells. Viability of the indicated cell lines in response to the dual HER2/EGFR inhibitor lapatinib (A) and the HER2-selective inhibitor tucatinib (B). Viability is expressed relative to vehicle-treated controls, set to 100%. All data were normally distributed and analyzed using two-tailed two-way ANOVA (A-B). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ vs. SCR (A); ### $p < 0.001$ vs. CB₂R KO (A).